

JCM CAA NL/FL & CAA DE: Programme

3rd of December, 2020

13:00	Opening	
	Machine learning, AI	
13:10	AI in times of COVID Creating quality pottery shape simulations for pre-training Machine Learning Pottery Image Classifiers: processes in the Arch-I-Scan project	Santos Nuñez Jareño (University of Leicester); Daniël P van Helden (University of Leicester)*; Penelope Allison (University of Leicester); Ivan Tyukin (University of Leicester)
13:30	Gaze and Body Orientation in Ancient Images. New Approaches for Estimating Relationships via Computer Vision	Torsten S. Bendschus (FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg)*; Ute Verstegen (FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg); Corinna Reinhardt (FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg); Lara Mührenberg (FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg); Prathmesh Madhu (Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg); Ronak Kosti (Pattern Recognition Lab, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg)
13:50	Patterns of Trauma - Employing AI and ML in bioarchaeological trauma research	Chiara G. M. Giroto (Independent Researcher / Ludwigs-Maximilians-University Munich)*; Henry C. W. Price (Imperial College London); Martin Trautmann (A&O Praxis für Bioarchäologie, München)
14:10	Using CarcassonNet to automatically detect and trace hollow roads in LiDAR data	Wouter B Verschoof-van der Vaart (Leiden University)*; Jürgen Landauer (Porsche)
14:30	Questions	
14:45	Break	
	Remote sensing and geophysics	
15:00	Searching for the Dutch castle landscape	Nancy de Jong-Lambregts (PhD)*; Ferry van den Oever (Saricon BV)
15:20	The tumultuous Marriage between Mrs. Archaeology and Mr. Geophysics	Joep Orbons (ArcheoPro)*
15:40	Drone thermography for archaeological applications	Jitte Waagen (Universiteit van Amsterdam)*
16:00	Questions	

4th of December, 2020

13:00	Opening	
	Gaming, AR and VR	
13:10	Augmented Blended Learning: providing immersive content to augment the museum environment	Markus H Stoffer (University of Amsterdam)*
13:30	Making historical VRs, lessons learned from two case-studies: the commanders house at Westerbork and the former Jewish neighbourhood Vlooienburg, Amsterdam.	Tijm Lanjouw (UvA)*; Jitte Waagen (Universiteit van Amsterdam)
13:50	Archaeogaming - Reflections on Code and the Playability of the Past	Sophie C. Schmidt (Deutsches Archäologisches Institut)*; Tine Rassalle (University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill)
14:10	Ship Shapes: Digitising 17th and 18th century Dutch ships	John McCarthy (Flinders University)*
14:30	Questions	
14:45	Break	
	Tools, statistics and little Minions	
15:00	Linked Open Samian Ware - Unveiling the hidden Data Dragons and uncovering temporal vagueness with the help of Little Minions	Florian Thiery (RGZM)*; Allard Mees (RGZM); Dennis Gottwald (Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz)
15:15	geoCore - QGIS plugin to construct a graphical representation of petrographic drilling profiles	Moritz Mennenga (Lower Saxony Institute for Historical Coastal Research)*; Gerrit Bette (T-Systems on site services GmbH)
15:30	The track graph: a heuristic tool for reconstructing past movement systems	Philip Verhagen (Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam)*; Laure Nuninger (UMR 6249 Laboratoire Chrono-Environnement, University of Bourgogne Franche-Comté)
15:50	Handmade pottery and the mystery of volume: how to calculate capacity in an accurate way	Vasiliki Lagari (Leiden University)*
16:10	The Fractal Dimension of Stone Tools	Florian Linsel (University of Cologne)*
16:30	Questions	
16:45	End	